

Workplace Diversity Issues in Business Enterprises: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the impact of diversity in the workplace is essential for leaders, managers, and organizations who strive to be competitive, creative and innovative in the new world of work. By recognizing the importance of sociocultural, situated and transformative learning perspectives in a diverse workplace, as well as the role of leaders and managers, progressive organizations can incorporate best practices for managing diversity and enjoy the benefits that this will bring. Our world of work is changing, including how we learn at work and the role of organizational leaders in creating inclusive environments that capitalize on individual strengths. There are many guidelines and suggestions for effective diversity management, and organizations that plan for diversity as well as recruit, train and motivate their work teams will place themselves advantageously to gain economic, managerial, social and educational returns on their diversity investment. Integrating these perspectives will allow companies to realize the range of benefits and opportunities that diversity brings and provide a fuller understanding of such an important and timely issue. The aim of this paper is to explore the common issues in diversity management, its effects on our world of work, and how to best manage diversity in that world.

Keywords: Diversity Management, Age Diversity, Gender Diversity, Ethnic Diversity

INTRODUCTION

Organizations need a more adaptable and qualified staff to be competitive in a quickly changing global economy that is characterized by the avalanche of technological innovation (Sing, 2004). As a result, finding highly qualified people becomes a strategic goal. The knowledge, skills, and attitudes required to fulfill corporate goals and gain a competitive advantage are therefore ensured by an organization's workforce diversity plan, which is a fundamental mechanism (Peteraf, 1993). Recent years have seen an increase in the importance of training due to the intensification of global competitiveness and the relative success of economies that place a strong focus on investing in training (Holden, 1997). In fact, HR managers stated that one of the biggest issues they faced at the beginning of the twenty-first century involved issues of training and development (Stavrou, Brewster & Charalambous, 2004).

The workplace diversity literature, according to O'Reilly, Williams, and Barsade (1998), supports three main theoretical frameworks for examining the potential effects of workplace diversity. The first is social categorization, which is defined by Turner (1987) as the division of individuals into groups based on distinctive characteristics such as gender, race, or age, which leads to stereotyping based on these distinctions. According to the attraction hypothesis, interpersonal attraction and attachment are increased by similarities on salient and non-salient characteristics like race or values (Berscheid & Walster, 2008). The third is the information and decision-making theory, which looks at how work-teams are affected by

the distribution of knowledge and competence. According to the Social Attraction Theory, businesses with more diverse workforces will be better able to compete in more diverse product markets and have more complicated business models and exceptional social resources (Richard & Johnson, 2000).

The performance implications of being acknowledged for workforce diversity management techniques, however, have received little consideration (Dick & Cassell, 2002).

The idea of diversity management implies using a variety of operational strategies to accommodate people from various social and cultural backgrounds. Henderson (1994) asserts that the idea also encompasses the use of sound managerial tactics to encourage the best possible use of human resources within a company. According to Cox (1993), the values and standards that are socially formed in society define the invisible components of variety. The government has put policies in place that guarantee equal employment opportunities for everyone in an effort to lessen racial and gender bias in the United States. Utilizing cultural innovations, ideas, and creativity to further business objectives is part of diversity management (Adler, 2005).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Diversity Management

Management of workforce diversity refers to the assortment of differences among personnel in a business (Jackson & Alvarez, 2000). A diverse and inclusive workplace is achieved through the application of best practices by organizations as part of their diversity management plan. According to a study by Albert (1994), diversity is attained through mentoring groups, supporting supplier diversity, and utilizing resource organizations' services, which support staff diversity. In the same vein, Jackson and Alvarez (1992) mention diversity committee use, diversity training, and awareness raising as effective strategies for promoting diversity.

Companies might use adoption as a way to increase employee diversity, according to Chatman Polzer, Barsade, and Neale (1998). The corporate strategic management concept suggests that diversity can be attained through empowering workers, hiring people from a variety of backgrounds, and ensuring the organization has strong leadership. Diversity can also be achieved by creating a culture that does not accept discrimination.

Diversity Issues in the Organization

Age Diversity

Families, higher education institutions, sports teams, and teams at work or in teams with members of different ages are just a few examples of groupings where age diversity is a common phenomenon (Kunze, Boehm & Bruch, 2013) explained that firms trying to recruit, retain, manage, and encourage quality employees face additional hurdles due to the workforce's unique generational variety. Every generation feels that its advantages are distinct from and do not improve upon those of earlier or later generations (Rowe, 2010). Age diversity has advantages for both the company and the personnel where it is practiced. An atmosphere with a range of ages fosters stronger working connections and improves social cohesiveness for all.

Workplace Generational Diversity Regardless of how different each person's experiences are, they all belong to the same generation in history. A generation is a group of people who were born and lived during the same time period and who share shared attitudes, tastes, knowledge, and experiences that have an impact on their views, values, and behaviors (Johnson & Johnson, 2010; Zemke, Raines, & Filipczak, 2013). Each generation brings different perceptions and expectations to the workplace. Expectations about their behavior, how they will manage others, and how their bosses or employers will handle them. Each of the four generations in the workforce has a strong work ethic, a unique perspective on the job, and a unique and preferred method of management. As a result, there are a lot older labor available as the population matures. As a result, middle-aged women are returning to the workforce, retirees are coming back to augment their pensions, and internship opportunities are attracting more young workers. According to Abrams & Von Frank (2014), as the labor force ages faster than it can be replaced, baby boomers are retiring or preparing to exit the labor market, there aren't enough members of generation X to

fill the void, and millennials are increasing in number. This section looks at how the various generations behave in the workplace and how they approach doing their jobs well.

Veterans or Traditionalist- born before 1943.

They are individuals who were young during the start of the Great Depression and World War II, and they approach the world with a positive outlook (Zemke, Raines & Filipczak, 2013). Despite all of its difficulties, this generation's foresight and dedication laid the groundwork for the society in which we currently reside and work. They revived a sagging economy and overcame the Great Depression. They have dominated world culture, and as a result, every other set of beliefs is compared to theirs. If a boss says, for example, that one of his or her younger workers lacks work ethics, what he or she is really expressing is that the younger generation lacks the traditional work ethic. Zemke, Raines, and Filipczak (2013) describe the following as the fundamental principles of traditionalists: honor, patience, devotion, sacrifice, hard work, duty before pleasure, adherence to rules, respect for authority, conformity, law and order. They put a strong emphasis on teamwork, are disciplined, respectful of authority, and prefer face-to-face communication. They go under many names, including Veterans, Matures, Silence, Loyalty, etc. They represent the tiniest fraction of the current global population. The majority of them currently work part-time, while some have retired. They have excellent communication skills, are fair and neutral, and firmly believe in the value of discussion. They enjoy serving as mediators. Although new generations criticize older generations and make derogatory remarks about them, the behavior that the elder generation accepts is regarded as the norm. Detail-oriented: They base their work on the information given to them. The traditionalists or veterans take care to complete duties carefully, efficiently, and effectively because they are dedicated to producing quality. Second, they frequently follow procedures and consistently carry out their assigned duties. They are the most devoted and devoted to the organization and its objectives, according to studies. They frequently find fulfillment in the work itself, and this fulfillment comes from performing the task competently. This implies that they get satisfaction in successfully completing a task. Both their professional and life experiences allow them to be practical for organizing. They have a cooperative and team-focused mentality.

The Baby Boomers- born between 1943-1960

These individuals were nurtured in an era of opportunity, tremendous optimism, and advancement. They were born during and after World War II. They are renowned for being logical, open to all, cooperative, goal-oriented, and extremely successful. Instead of sharing leadership, they place a higher priority on experience, listening, and encouraging. Although they support participative leadership, they find it difficult to delegate. They prefer to maintain the status quo (Abrams & Von Frank, 2014).

Generation X- born between 1960-1980

People who were born after the baby boomers' first flush and who grew up amid the boomers' shadows and the rise of the Asian tiger make up this generation. Generation Xers are capable leaders who excel under pressure. They are leaders who are fair, straightforward, observant, pragmatic, and strategic and dislike creating vision statements or holding meetings. Instead, they guide their teams by assigning them tasks that require critical thought and help the group reach wise decisions. They want to remove barriers, let people handle their own work, then provide comments and distribute credit. Their best qualities are the capacity to observe, recognize unmet needs, hide emotions when appropriate, act quickly when the situation warrants it, and ensure that whatever others try actually accomplishes what they set out to do. They think that the greatest way to succeed is to take incredible risks. Generation Xers are the ideal candidates for the job, for example, if a manager or employer wants to get things done without caring how they were done in an organization. They are able to discriminate between errors that are significant and those that are not. As leaders, they are shrewd, adaptable, and skilled with timing. They have a straightforward manner, good judgment, and agility.

Generation Y or the Millennials: born between 1980 - 2004: They are the descendants of Baby Boomers and early Xers, who were raised in a society that valued, fostered, and safeguarded children. The newest generation to enter the workforce is this one. They view and revere their parents as role models. They are incredibly reliant on technology and social media, such as Facebook, Twitter, and others, and

they make and have friends all over the world who they can get in touch with whenever they want. When they first started working, they noticed how packed the workplace was with generation X and older workers who hadn't yet retired. The fact that this generation works to achieve more than just a paycheck is one of its traits. They seek out positions and businesses that are invested in helping them accomplish their own objectives. Millennials readily leave jobs they don't like in favor of another, unlike older generations (such as generation Xers and generation Yers) who wait patiently for promotions or better prospects (Grubb, 2016). Although the millennial generation is energetic and brings new energy to the company, they also present obstacles. Due to their upbringing, they anticipate a work to be personalized for them. They frequently seek just-in-time information, and they recognize and value coaching as a way to get it. The millennial generation may be under 30, but according to Abrams & Von Frank (2014), they have a lot to say. They constantly want to be taken seriously and heard. The millennial generation is strong in terms of leadership because they are competent, selfless, and sensible leaders. They do not oppose change; rather, they view it favorably and as something that is good. Even if they view change as a positive, they nonetheless consider other people's opinions and their stance on the change. Their collaborative skills training is beneficial for fostering community and consensus (Abrams & Von Frank, 2014). According to Johnson & Johnson (2010), this group of people doesn't value the nine to five workdays set by the company. Instead, they are more engaged and active when they can choose their own working hours. Thirdly, they are highly keen to start contributing to the company as soon as they join since they are aware of how quickly technology is evolving and are therefore very interested in constantly improving their skills. Last but not least, as long as people believe that the organization supports their interests, they quickly become devoted and loyal to it.

The Impact of Age Diversity

a. Creativity and Innovation

In the face of competition, in particular, age diversity has been determined to be a crucial and strategic capability that contributes (if not really produces) value to the company (Darwin, 2014). Facilitating creativity and innovation is one way that age diversity adds value to the company and improves overall performance. While innovation is the deliberate introduction of innovative ideas, methods, and processes into a work team, creativity refers to the development of novel ideas that are both beneficial and acceptable (Rietzchel&Zacher, 2015).

However, despite an increase in empirical studies on age and work, Rietzchel and Zacher (2015) argue that research on the relationship between age and creativity or innovation has not been constrained. Nevertheless, some research on the topic has discovered a link between the organization's age diversity, creativity, and innovativeness in terms of ideas, practices, and processes (Rietzchel&Zacher, 2015; Darwin&Palanisamy, 2015). According to other studies, people of different ages behave more creatively. According to Simons and Rowland (2011), variety results in diverse viewpoints, knowledge, and abilities that foster creativity and innovation and reduce adherence to traditional and current standards. According to Gupta (2013), age-heterogeneous workforces are more imaginative and creative than more homogeneous ones because the values that people of different age groups possess complement one another.

Due to widespread misconceptions around the topic of age, however, age diversity may not necessarily produce favorable results on organizational performance. Older workers, according to some misconceptions, tend to have greater health issues, are less able to adapt to technological advancements and organizational changes, and generally provide lower returns on investment (Tolbize, 2008). In fact, recent research has revealed that more Age diversity has a negligible impact on the company's total production.

b. Decision Making and Problem Solving Propensity

Making decisions involves a variety of conscious cognitive processes that take into account environmental factors in a particular situation and period of time (Cardelle-Elawar, Irwin & Sanz de AcedoLizarraga, 2007). It is crucial for the smooth operation of the organization because it serves as its

pivot. Making decisions also involves interacting with the issue at hand in a particular situation and the issue that has to be resolved. Age diversity is a crucial asset in contemporary organizations, according to Zaidi, Saif, and Zaheer (2010). He goes on to say that elder employees contribute a crucial set of experiences and intuition that aid in decision-making due to their intuition and experience.

Young employees are equally important in decision-making in modern organizations, according to Darwin (2014), because they are more knowledgeable about the information and technology components of the current corporate environment. Therefore, it may be claimed that a workforce with a mix of generations that includes both older and younger workers is essential for making important decisions and coming up with novel solutions to problems.

According to Glass (2007), top management and leadership in businesses nowadays take advantage of the firm's age diversity. As a result, they are able to make a variety of selections that could be useful after taking into account the viewpoints offered by such a diverse staff. Furthermore, Zaidi et al. (2010) assert that age variability in the workforce increases the amount of creativity in the concepts from which the company's top management is able to define and implement creative solutions in advance of or in response to issues. It also implies that teamwork among age-heterogeneous groups can result in high-quality decisions.

Within a diverse workgroup, it is also feasible to reach consensus in response to a challenge or disagreement (Tolbize, 2008). According to Dezo and Ross (2013) age diversity may not necessarily facilitate problem resolution or promote informed decision-making. They draw attention to the fact that, if not handled properly, these differences and the stereotypes that highlight them have the potential to become a real source of conflict. Simons and Rowland (2011) agree and point to the social attraction paradigm, which believes that a more homogeneous group is better equipped to solve problems and reach conclusions. As a group's values, viewpoints, experiences, and possibly skills become the focal focus for intergroup communication, it follows that the possibility of communication issues within a group with a greater age diversity is extremely significant (Darwin, 2014; Tolbize, 2008).

c. Quality Delivery

Age diversity and aspects of organizational performance like good decision-making, creativity, and innovation have been linked by prior studies. Therefore, age diversity ought to have an effect on the standard of services and goods that a company offers. According to Mutunga and Gachunga (2013), worker age diversity in a corporation supports the upward (reverse mentoring) and downward (mentoring) interchange of information and ideas across the generational groups. This is in reference to succession planning for businesses. These discussions result in modifications to or maintenance of the level of quality of a company's services or goods.

In fact, according to Darwin and Palanisamy's (2015) observations, the various viewpoints, knowledge, and experiences that individuals from various age groups contribute to the product or service development may result in a significant improvement in the quality of the good or service that the company ultimately produces. An age-diverse workforce has advantages in terms of producing high-quality goods and services, according to research by Parrotta, Pozzoli, and Pytlikova from 2011. They contend that in order to produce high-quality products and services that successfully reach the target market, younger employees must bring their expertise in information technology (IT), while older employees must bring a deeper comprehension of market dynamics. Age variety thus fosters an environment in which generational expertise, knowledge, and experience are tapped into the production process, resulting in the production of good and high-quality products. Alesina and La Ferrara (2005) make a similar argument, contending that a workforce with a diverse range of ages fosters greater innovation and productivity, which leads to better products and services and higher company productivity.

Gender Diversity

According to Powell (2011), gender is the physiological inference of a person being either male or female, including expectations and ideas about what types of attitudes, behaviors, values, knowledge, abilities, and interest areas are more appropriate for or typical of one sex than the other. The focus of gender diversity research is on how people perceive differences between men and women. The way that

people respond to other people's behaviors in the workplace or any other group alliance is affected by these gender variances. Prejudice, preconceptions, and discrimination all show signs of gender diversity. Organizational research has been increasingly important in recent years as it relates to the organizational barriers that prevent women from reaching the highest levels of their careers. In their study, Singh and Vinnicombe (2004) found that women are almost, if not entirely, underrepresented in top positions in businesses. However, male directors frequently constitute an elite group at the top of the corporate world, and despite making progress into middle management, relatively few women are able to break past this glass ceiling and join this elite group. Organizational research has been increasingly important in recent years as it relates to the organizational barriers that prevent women from reaching the highest levels of their careers. In their study, Singh and Vinnicombe (2004) found that women are almost, if not entirely, underrepresented in top positions in businesses. However, male directors frequently constitute an elite group at the top of the corporate world, and despite making progress into middle management, relatively few women are able to break past this glass ceiling and join this elite group.

The phrase "glass ceiling" has become one of the most frequently used metaphors to explain why women are underrepresented in senior organizational positions. The term "glass ceiling" was created in the 1960s, according to Mavin (2016), who cited Morrinson & Von Glinow (1990). This term is used to describe a subtle barrier that can prevent women from advancing up the managerial ladder while being so obvious and strong. Glass ceiling is a term used to describe organizational rules and procedures that make it difficult and restrictive for women to hold the highest positions in their particular fields. Despite seeing the pinnacle of the managerial structure, women may be unable to advance there (Gatrell & Swan, 2008).

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The glass ceiling seems to prevent women from advancing to top management positions solely due to their gender (Powell, 2011). Powell continues by saying that the average full-time salary for a woman is still lower than for a man in the same profession. In most organizations, women's economic status continues to be lower than men's. The difference in average pay between workers in male- and female-dominated occupations is one factor contributing to this discrepancy. Glass ceiling is not a barrier that women face because they are unable to handle jobs in upper-level management. Instead, the barrier prevents women from moving up the corporate ladder just because they are female. For corporations, removing the "glass ceiling" and other barriers to women's achievement is a significant task. Therefore, organizations require policies that encourage equal pay and other benefit programs for women; rules that encourage equal pay for positions of equal value and encourage additional benefit programs of particular importance to women.

The Impact of Gender Diversity

a. Quality of Organizational Management and Leadership

The effect of gender diversity in top management and organizational leadership on the overall performance of the organization is a hot topic of discussion. According to Chin (2013), a study revealed that businesses with high levels of gender diversity in top leadership experienced notable anomalous returns. While the majority of top leadership and management in most organizations is held by men, Van Knippenberg, De Dreu, and Homan (2014) discovered that adding women to these teams not only makes them more diverse but also raises the caliber of the top-level management and leadership.

Three significant factors have likely contributed to the rise in gender diversity in senior management teams. These include a shift in the percentage of women holding board-level roles, an increase in government intervention, and a shift in the focus of discussions on gender from one of equality and justice to one of superior performance, according to the Research Institute (2012). According to Van Knippenberg, et al. (2014), gender diversity enhances managerial information processing and decision making of the managerial team, leading to effective strategy formulation and decision making key processes. This argument supports the idea that gender diversity improves the quality of organizational leadership and management. Due to the combination of gender-based perspectives expressed by both males and females in the managerial teams, Nakagwa (2015) discovered that gender diversity in the workforce, along with other kinds of diversity, provided more innovative and higher-quality solutions.

In other words, gender diversity adds a range of perspectives to crucial managerial and strategic leadership decisions, improving their quality and potential efficacy for the company. According to Dezo and Ross (2012), heterogeneous groups (in terms of gender) contribute a variety of viewpoints and experiences that help managers and leaders in these positions make judgments that are of a high caliber. The authors go on to hypothesize that the sheer presence of a woman on the top management team who is knowledgeable about the problem at hand may encourage a wider and more in-depth discussion of potential solutions (TMT).

In terms of leadership philosophies, organizational leadership may also be advantageous. According to research, there are differences between men and women's managerial behavioral propensities (Van Knippenberg, et al., 2014). According to Dezo and Ross (2012), men tend to have less interactive leadership styles that are more concerned with goal fulfillment and limited participation, whereas women tend to emphasize inclusion, participation, and power sharing. Therefore, having a leadership style that is a combination of the managerial behavioral and leadership tendencies of men and women may benefit a company with a moderate to high gender diversity.

b. Competitive Advantage

The resource-based perspective, according to Ali, Metz, and Kulik (2007), asserts that a corporation can obtain a sustained competitive advantage (C.A.) by making use of the valuable, rare, unique, and non-sustainable (VRIN) resources. The VRIN resources that can give the company a competitive edge are correlated with gender diversity. These resources are listed by Ali, et al. (2007) and include creativity and invention, increased problem solving, and market insight. The team's general market insight, creativity, and innovation may all be improved by having a gender diverse workforce. A varied workgroup, according to Darwin and Palanisamy (2015), delivers a variety of experiences, skill sets, and insights that improve overall team performance and advance organizational performance.

Diversity is a strategic source for achieving competitive advantage, according to studies. For instance, Raza, Ishtiaqi, Kanwal, Butt, and Nawaz (2013) discovered that age, gender, and educational diversity all had a favorable impact on an organization's competitive edge. Studies have shown that mixed gender groups perform better than same gender groups, according to Darwin and Palanisamy (2015). In this sense, it is debatable whether or not organizations with a more diversified gender makeup of their staff have a competitive edge over those with a more homogeneous gender workforce. According to Ali et al.(2007) .'s analysis of gender diversity and decision-making, gender diversity improves an organization's C.A. by making it easier to make wise decisions.

An organization can build its strategic goals on the range of viewpoints, abilities, and information that a more gender diverse staff delivers to the company (Ali, et al., 2013). When it comes to decision-making, such a range of viewpoints is essential. The high-quality, well-informed decisions that arise give the company a competitive edge when it comes to researching the market and formulating a successful business plan.

Ethnic Diversity

An ethnic group could be thought of as a collection of people who follow similar cultural traditions and customs and who also give its members a sense of national identity (Sayers, 2012). Language, religion, race, and cultural variation are all implied by the term "ethnic diversity." In order to improve and increase

both employee satisfaction and business success, there has been a growth in the organization's multicultural workforce. When it comes to team performance in terms of business results, such as sales, profit, and market share, a moderate level of ethnic diversity has little impact. However, increasing ethnic diversity has a beneficial effect on performance if at least the majority of the team members are from varied backgrounds (Gupta, 2013). Following the recent growth in diversity, there has also been a surge in work groups with the goal of increasing participation to improve overall employee and organizational performance. Although the makeup of the workforce is rapidly diversifying in terms of race, age, gender, education, and other factors, there has also been an increase in interest in how these differences affect academic institutions (Watzon, Johnson & Zgourides, 2002).

The rise of diverse cultures in society has led to an increase of multi-cultural organizations, which has spread through ancestral, educational, and religious circles. According to Watzon, Johnson, and Zgourides (2002), teams perform better when their members come from a variety of cultural backgrounds. This is seen as a benefit of embracing different ethnic perspectives for problem-solving and improving the outcomes of team members after they have learned how to use their differences for their advantage. Having demographic diversities in terms of race/ethnicity, nationality, gender, and age, per Harrison & Klein (2007), can have detrimental effects on businesses. It is significant to note that people from minority groups are more likely to feel or experience discrimination, have identity issues, be dissatisfied with their jobs, be less committed to the organization, and have these issues.

Milliken & Martins (2000) However, most of the issues that are faced tend to disappear as the minority group expands. According to Timmermans, Ostergaard, and Kristinsson's (2011) research, ethnicity can stand in for or replace cultural background, and ethnic dissimilarity can foster positive creative and inventive performance among members since it broadens employees' perspectives within the organization. According to Timmermans, Ostergaard, and Kristinsson's (2011) research, while a low level of ethnic diversity may be positively correlated with creativity and innovation, a high level of ethnic diversity may have the opposite effect because it tends to divide people into subgroups based on social categorization, lead to employee conflict, and undermine teamwork. (Dahlin Weingart & Hinds, 2005).

Instead of something that can be forced on someone by simply looking at them and passing judgment on who they are based solely on how they seem, ethnicity is a self-identification of sociocultural identity (Sayers, 2012). According to the social identity theory, ethnicity can be used to rapidly categorize a group of people into different ethnic backgrounds because it is a surface-level characteristic of variety. People usually identify with their ethnic heritage because it provides them a sense of belonging and links them to a community of others who have a common background. It is thought that individuals favor those who share their racial or ethnic heritage more than other individuals.

The Impact of Ethnic Diversity

a. Employee Productivity

Productivity is essential for long-term profitability and competitiveness in almost all firms (Muchiti & Gachunga, 2015). Productivity is a way to quantify how well resources are utilized in a business to achieve a specific set of organizational goals (Ofoegbu, Olawepo & Ibojo, 2013). Productivity is typically defined as the qualitative relationship between the resources employed in production and the output of a specific production. To put it another way, it is the proportion of input to output (Muchiti & Gachunga, 2015). The productivity decreases when the ratio decreases, and vice versa. Productivity is a term that, when used in relation to employees, is challenging to define and quantify (Ofoegbu, et al., 2013).

According to Muchiti and Gachunga (2015), there are four variables that can be utilized as measures of employee productivity. These include a rise in productivity, employee inspiration, job satisfaction, and the caliber of the goods or services. According to Nnabuife (2009), motivation may be viewed as the external and internal driving forces that provide the willingness to engage in an activity through to its successful completion. Employee motivation is, thus, the readiness of the employee to carry out a task with the fullest attention in order to support the achievement of a predetermined organizational goal.

Efficiency is a process' or activity's efficiency or effectiveness, which leads to the complete and whole accomplishment of a predetermined objective (Darwin & Palanisamy, 2015). The degree of contentment a worker feels with their position and how well they carry out the tasks given to them is referred to as their level of job satisfaction. Product or service quality refers to an item's capacity to live up to or even beyond client expectations. According to Rasul and Rogger (2015), ethnic diversity has an impact on productivity through influencing employee happiness, the level of efficiency in the company, employee motivation for their work, and the caliber of goods and services a firm produces.

Ethnic variety is one of the most pertinent and noticeable aspects of labor heterogeneity, according to Hoogendoorn & van Praag (2012). Ethnic diversity was described as the variation in (mother) or principal languages, races, faiths, and civilizations measured in terms of the nation of birth of the individual, their parents, or both. A variety of information sets, standards, skill levels, and knowledge are used to highlight it (Morgan & Vardy, 2009). Therefore, ethnic diversity may have an impact on how motivated employees are at work, how effective the company is, how satisfied employees are with their jobs, and the caliber of goods and services a company provides.

According to Darwin (2014), ethnic diversity improves organizational performance by creating a pool of skill sets and learning opportunities that the company may draw from to achieve better performance outcomes. Ethnic diversity has a similar effect on organizational performance, claims Gupta (2013). Ostergaard, Timmermans, and Kristinsson (2011) discovered that ethnic diversity improves creativity and innovation in the firm by broadening perspectives and viewpoints. This finding lends support to this position. According to several research, an ethnically diverse workforce is more creative and innovative than one that is more homogeneous (Darwin & Palanisamy, 2015). This is presumably due to the benefits that racial diversity in the workplace offers in terms of learning opportunities, viewpoints, and complementary skills.

Ethnic diversity is connected to or correlates with a range of knowledge bases, social norms, skills, and capacities that help to enhance organizational decision-making and problem-solving (Darwin & Palanisamy, 2015). Ethnic diversity is also intimately connected to team and organization innovative performance, according to Ostergaard et al (2011) .'s argument.

However, Gupta (2013) found that more ethnic diversity had a detrimental effect on problem resolution and communication. Despite the strenuous efforts to eliminate the intrinsic ethnic inequalities that exist in an ethnically diverse workforce, Kellough and Naff (2004) maintain that the issue is entrenched. Using the ethnic identity theory as support, they argue that individuals have a propensity to create ethnic identities and identify with persons from their own ethnic group.

This is related to the self-categorization and social identity theories, which observe a propensity for individuals with similar racial, gender, and age characteristics to establish homogenous groups and regard as outsiders those who are different from them (Ali, et al., 2011). One of the main destabilizing aspects in an ethnically varied workforce is the development of ethnic identities and the resulting sense of in-groups vs out-groups, which can negatively impact employee job satisfaction, morale, and overall organizational performance (Gupta, 2013; Ali, et al., 2011).

Cultural Diversity

The demographic, socioeconomic, and cultural distinctions that are present in society are reflected in the workplace through cultural diversity (Gotsis and Korte 2015). Diversity management is seen at the European Union level as a key tenet of the Europe 2020 plan for building a resilient and inclusive economy (European Commission, 2012). This is because it is believed that firms can profit much from successful diversity management, including an increase in creativity, a rise in employee satisfaction and retention, a rise in customer engagement, etc (European Commission, 2012).

The global economy, which has brought about the internationalization of businesses and a shift in the composition of the workforce, mostly through immigration and guest workers, has made the concern for cultural diversity a priority at the organizational level. Additionally, global anti-discrimination legal trends compel businesses to implement similar policies with regard to their personnel (Mor Barak, 2014).

In order to take advantage of the benefits of a diverse workforce, a number of initiatives, policies, and interventions are created on an organizational level (Gotsis and Korte 2015).

Most frequently, these are seen in human resource practices, such as growing numbers of workers from minority or vulnerable groups (based on criteria such as ethnicity, race, or gender), mentoring, educational and diversity training programs (such as diversity and cultural awareness), and work-life balance programs for vulnerable groups (such as women, people with certain religious affiliations, the elderly, etc.) (Gotsis and Korte 2015). The extant literature in this area of inquiry, which has only lately emerged into a scholarly topic, reflects this concern for workplace cultural diversity (approximately 30 years ago). Thus, scholarly interest in the topic has increased by more than 110 percent over the past ten years compared to the preceding decade, while in the public press, interest has increased by about 500 percent since the field's early years in the mid-1980s (Jonsen, Maznevski and Schneider, 2011).

Religious Diversity

While incorporating equality and diversity into their fundamental values, organizations have started to recognize the benefits of religious and cultural diversity. For instance, Melayu Islam Beraja (Malay Muslim Monarchy), a national philosophy that embraces the Malay culture of Brunei, Islamic principles, and the history and function of monarchy, is something that local and international enterprises in Brunei are obliged to take into account. According to Islamic religious and regional cultural beliefs, Melayu Islam Beraja advocates the idea that people should be treated like family members both inside and outside of organizations (Low & Mohd Zain, 2008). Similar to this, Alliance Bank Malaysia incorporates cultural diversity into its core values and works to develop a strong staff while accomplishing its corporate objectives (Alliance Bank, 2014). In Ireland, where community national schools with a variety of religious, denominational, and cultural beliefs are encouraged, there is a comparable dedication to religious pluralism. These schools are said to provide a multid denominational approach to religious instruction, accommodating all worldviews during the school day. In actuality, they resemble a cross between conventionally religious schools and the expanding "Educate Together" model, which forbids the teaching of religion in schools (Donnelly, 2017).

Religion is frequently a problem at work as companies become increasingly diverse. Conflicts between company policies and employees' religious beliefs can result in issues (Mathis et al., 2016). For instance, certain businesses might dictate how their staff should dress. But due to their religious beliefs, some men and women would find this unacceptable. This is likely the case with headgear like the turban worn by Sikhs and the hijab worn by some Muslim women. Similar to this, some workers could find it difficult to work on certain days and hours owing to religious obligations like the Sabbath and Ramadan (Hambler, 2015).

People of all faiths, including Muslims, Sikhs, and Jews, are affected by the persistent problem of religious discrimination in Western businesses (Moodie, 2016). Lack of understanding of various religious and cultural beliefs is a common cause of the issue, which can result in misunderstandings and hostility. As a result, workers may run into issues with not only one another but also their religious duties and work (Byrd & Scott, 2014). Some of the discriminatory or exclusive behaviors may not be willful and malicious, but they could reflect a lack of workplace diversity awareness (Mor Barak, 2014). These problems frequently represent the surface of deeper problems, i.e., behavioural outcomes that may influence organizational performance as well as employee engagement and commitment (Bendl et al., 2015).

Religious diversity may cause significant workplace disputes if it is not well understood and handled, according to prior study (Byrd & Scott, 2014; Gebert et al., 2014). Christians, for instance, might not want to work on their traditional religious or celebratory holidays, whereas practicing Muslims could need one to three brief breaks each day for required prayers (Chapman et al., 2014; Yasmeen & Markovic, 2014). As a result, managing religious diversity at work requires organizational flexibility as well as diversity management.

Understanding the laws and religious obligations and striking a balance between organizational needs and employee preferences regarding exercising their religion at work may be necessary for the resolution of some religion-related issues (Bendl et al., 2015). Organizations, particularly in Western nations, are interested in developing strategies and management interventions to mitigate negative organizational and individual consequences of religious discrimination in the workplace due to anti-discrimination legislation in a number of countries and jurisdictions (Chapman et al., 2014; Messarra, 2014).

Businesses are starting to see the advantages of integrating spirituality into their workplaces (Garcia-Zamor, 2003). According to researcher Garcia-Zamor (2003), embracing religion at work is considered as a "win-win" situation because raising employee satisfaction will boost organizational results like productivity. For instance, Garcia-Zamor (2003) cites a company's policy to provide recurrent 20–30 minute paid meditation breaks, which shown an improvement in organizational dedication and performance. Additionally, businesses looking to hire the best workers may view the acceptance of religion in the workplace as a competitive advantage (King & Holmes, 2012). The idea of spirituality and faith in the workplace is of growing interest among management studies, according to researchers King and Holmes (2012). This is because perceived organizational fit has been associated more strongly with people who share similar values. Increases in job satisfaction, job attraction, turnover, and performance ratings would follow from this perceived fit (Benefiel, Fry, & Geigle, 2014).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The present day working environment is turning out to be more diverse. Many organizations today endeavor to advance comprehensiveness of under-represented groups through proactive endeavors in order to create an environment where each employee is esteemed and their talents fully utilized to meet both individual and organizational goals. The capabilities of both genders and various diverse groups, offer a wider labour pool. An organization with a capacity to draw in and hold qualified people through reasonable and balanced professional success is certainly going to gain competitive advantage.

The study makes the following recommendations:

- i. Age Diversity can lift organizations to new horizons, achieve more goals and be more successful. Different generations can have different communication styles and norms. Hence organizations should plan and implement fun hangouts, leisure activities, official dine-outs, lunches and so on, where employees from all age-groups are invited, an organization provide a friendly and enjoyable work environment which will enhance the interchange and cross fertilization of ideas.
- ii. Organizations should endeavour to remove every subtle obstacle that hinders women from climbing up the managerial ladder. All forms of organizational practices and processes which create difficulties and limitations for women attaining the highest position of their particular field must be effectively removed.
- iii. It is important that effective workplace strategies and policies be designed, implemented and monitored, in order not only to eliminate racial discrimination but also to support a more diverse workforce. Employing a diverse workforce – and managing it effectively – not only satisfies legal, ethical obligations, but is also good for business.
- iv. Organizations should put in place policies to accommodate workers from diverse backgrounds so as to minimize the negative potential legal and financial consequences and also key to the enterprise's adaptability, growth, sustainability and competitive edge.

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